

AN INNOVATIVE WOVEN 3D BASALT TEXTILE AS REINFORCEMENT IN TRC: A FLEXURAL COMPARISON, WEFT VS WARP

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the flexural behavior of Textile Reinforced Cement (TRC) using uncoated woven basalt textiles. Four different TRC configurations were compared in a four-point bending test using Digital Image Correlation (DIC): 2D weft, 2D warp, 3D weft, and 3D warp. Compositions with 2D reinforcements performed mechanically better than ones with 3D, and reinforcement in the warp direction showed higher failure load and displacement than in the weft direction. These unexpected results are related to the sensitivity of the loadbearing behavior to inaccurate textile positioning, particularly within very thin cross sections and for low fiber volume fractions.

KEYWORDS

Basalt textiles, Woven textiles, Four-point bending, Digital Image Correlation (DIC), Textile orientation

INTRODUCTION

Textile Reinforced Cement (TRC) is a material with growing interest that has been widely studied as a lightweight construction material in recent years. The benefits of TRC lie in the potential optimal use of its cross-section in loading applications. The textile reinforcements can vary in composition or geometry depending on the application (Aveston et al., 1971; Brameshuber, 2006; Peled et al., 2017). Textile reinforcements come in many materials and types. Current research focuses mainly on the mechanical behavior of TRC with glass or carbon fibers used as reinforcement. In this study, the choice was put on basalt fibers, which have numerous advantages over glass fibers. Basalt fibers have a similar tensile strength as glass fibers and are only slightly more subjective to alkali attack than AR-glass, according to literature (Wang et al., 2021). Their properties also stay constant during use at high temperatures; basalt fibers can be used until 650°C without loss in strength (300°C for glass fibers) (Horrocks, 2016). Its price is also much lower than carbon fibers, which can provide an acceptable alternative when such extreme properties are unnecessary.

Studies showed the benefits of using three-dimensional (3D) textiles as reinforcement by comparing them to the more commonly used two-dimensional (2D) textiles, such as the ease of manufacturing and the stronger anchorage given by the transversal connections, leading to better mechanical properties and post-cracking behavior (Amzaleg et al., 2013; El Kadi et al., 2020). Others looked at the improved strength in flexural behavior for textiles used in the weft direction compared to the warp direction (El Kadi et al., 2020; Haik et al., 2017). The coating of the textiles also plays an essential role in the strength of the textiles (by themselves or in the composite) but also in the anchorage and transfer of forces between the fibers and the cement matrix. A coated fiber bundle will behave like a single thick fiber, while an uncoated fiber bundle will not perfectly transfer the load from the outside fibers to the interior fibers. Coating the fibers improves the load transfer and mechanical performance (Dvorkin et al., 2013; Nadv et al., 2017).

This study will focus on the flexural behavior of TRC with woven basalt fibers. Basalt fibers have not yet been studied in depth in literature, although they look promising for applications at both ambient

and elevated temperatures. To do so, uncoated woven textiles will be used in this research. Parameters such as the geometry of the textile (2D vs. 3D) and the orientation of the reinforcements (weft vs. warp) will be studied to see their influence on the flexural properties of the TRC.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The TRC specimens in this study were made of 2D and 3D woven basalt textiles. The geometry of the textiles can be seen in Figure 1, and the properties of the fiber bundle and textiles can be found respectively in Table 1 and Table 2. The fibers have a silane sizing applied after manufacturing, but the textiles do not have an additional coating. The weft direction of the textile is composed of only basalt fiber bundles. In contrast, the warp direction has an additional polyester fiber bundle to keep the mesh in place during weaving.

Table 1: Properties of the fiber bundle composing the textile

Type of fiber	Tex	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Specific gravity (g/m ³)	Young's Modulus (GPa)
Basalt	1200	830	2	2.69	69
Polyester	668	603	24	1.38	10

Table 2: Properties of the woven textiles

Textiles	Material	Mesh size (mm x mm)	Uncoated density (g/m ²)	Specific gravity (g/m ³)	Transversal connection
Woven 2D	Basalt-Polyester	9.1 x 9.1	335	2.69	None
Woven 3D	Basalt-Polyester	9.5 x 15 or 9.5 x 7.1	709	2.69	Woven polyester

The matrix chosen for the TRC is a commercially available mortar grout (Sikagrout-312) that has a high flowability and therefore allows for a good impregnation of the fibers during the casting process. The properties of the mortar can be found in Table 3.

Table 3: Properties of the mortar grout (obtained from experiment)

Name	Maximum aggregate size (mm)	Water/mortar ratio	Specific gravity (g/m ³)	Compressive strength (28d) (MPa)	Modulus of rupture (28d) (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)
SikaGrout-312	2	0.144	2.3	80.5 ± 3.7	6 ± 0.5	33.1 ± 5.0

Four different configurations of TRC are compared in this study: 2D reinforcements with the weft direction aligned with the loading direction (2D_We), 2D reinforcements with the warp direction aligned with the loading direction (2D_Wa), 3D reinforcements with the weft direction aligned with the loading direction (3D_We), and 3D reinforcements with the warp direction aligned with the loading direction (3D_Wa). The specimens in this research have either one 3D textile or two equivalent layers of 2D textiles placed at corresponding locations over the thickness. Both correspond to 12 reinforcing fiber bundles (six per layer) in the loading direction. The samples with 3D textiles have a dimension of 450 x 60 x 17 mm, resulting in a fiber volume fraction of 0.52%, while for samples with 2D textiles, the thickness is 18 mm, resulting in a slightly lower volume fraction of 0.48%.

Specimen manufacturing

Due to the difference in geometry between the 2D and 3D textiles (see Figure 1. c), distinct casting methods have been used for each type of textile.

The casting of the 2D textiles was done in a mold that allows for clamping the textiles between the different parts of the mold (Figure 2. a). This process requires cutting the textiles to the correct dimensions and carefully placing them in the mold to have the same number of reinforcement fibers (6 per layer) in the longitudinal direction. However, the mold allows the positioning of the textile layer at 2 mm from the bottom side of the samples and, therefore, samples with immediately the correct dimensions (Figure 2. c).

Figure 2: TRC casting process

On the other hand, the casting of specimens with 3D textiles requires another approach. The division of the textiles to have the required reinforcement ratio must be done along the X formed by the polyester bundles (see Figure 1. b). This makes it impossible to clamp the 3D textiles as it was done for the 2D ones. Therefore, a bigger mold of 500 x 500 mm (length x width) was used. The 3D textiles cut slightly smaller than the mold was placed on top of sticks that ensure a spacing of 2 mm from the bottom of the mold. In this method, the 3D samples are cut out from the plate instead of being made to the correct dimensions from the start.

In both casting methods, a thin layer of oil was applied at the bottom of the molds before placing the textiles. The textiles were aligned as straight as possible with the mold, thus, the samples' loading direction. A spacing of 2 mm between the inferior layer of the textiles and the bottom of the mold was ensured so that the mortar could flow underneath. After placing the textiles, the mortar grout was poured on top of the textile until the mold was filled. The filling process was done on a vibrating table to allow the trapped air bubbles to escape the matrix and ensure good mortar penetration into the textiles. A plastic film was applied on top of the mortar, and the molds were closed with a wooden plate and left to cure for seven days at room temperature. After this time, all specimens were de-molded, put in plastic wrap, and placed in a room with a constant temperature of 20°C to finish curing until 28 days of age.

Once fully cured, the 3D TRCs were cut to the correct length and width of 450 x 60 mm (Figure 2. d). The utmost care was put into the cutting process so that the 3D TRC samples would each have the correct amount of longitudinal reinforcements. All samples were painted white on the side and bottom, and a speckle pattern was applied for DIC analysis.

It was observed after the cutting of the 3D_We samples that the reinforcements in the loaded section were positioned higher than expected (see Figure 3). The distance between the bottom reinforcements and the bottom of the section was 5 mm instead of 2 mm. This change will be taken into consideration in the results.

Figure 3: Side view of samples 1 and 2 of 3D_We

Six specimens were prepared for each configuration, with the three added preliminary samples of 3D_We-t. In total, 27 specimens were tested.

Four-point bending test setup

The four-point bending tests were conducted on an Instron 8502 bench with a load cell of 10 kN (see Figure 4). The distance between the supports was 350 mm, and the loading span was 100 mm. The crosshead rate was put at 2 mm/min. The setup presented in Figure 4 used two Digital Image Correlation (DIC) systems (Schreier et al., 2009). The first one monitored the full-field displacement and strain from the side of the specimen, while the second monitored the samples' bottom face to focus on the formation of the cracks. The software VIC-Snap from Correlated Solutions was used to make the acquisition of the pictures and the post-processing analysis was done with the software Vic-3D 9, also from Correlated Solutions.

a) DIC monitoring of the side of the sample

b) DIC monitoring of the bottom of the sample

Figure 4: Four-point bending setup

RESULTS

Mechanical behavior

The experimental load vs. displacement curves recorded by DIC for the different TRC compositions are shown in Figure 5, and Figure 6 compares one typical curve from each composition. All specimens failed due to tensile failure of the reinforcing fibers; no other failure mode was observed. The flexural tests show that all the samples go through the pre-cracking stage, during which the mechanical behavior is dictated by the composite effect of the matrix and the reinforcing textile. This is followed by the multiple-cracking stage, where the matrix cracks and the load is redistributed to the textile

reinforcements. Finally, some of the samples go to a post-cracking stage where the loaded section of the samples is saturated with cracks, which start to open further; some cracks also start forming along the length of the sample outside of the loaded section. Since all 3D_We samples did not have a post-cracking stage, samples with the same properties but from an earlier batch (3D_We-t) were also used for comparison. The flexural parameters for each configuration have been calculated and are given in Table 4.

Figure 5: Scaled load vs. displacement curves for all tested samples

From Figure 5, it can directly be seen that the geometry and the orientation of the reinforcement layer greatly influenced the mechanical behavior of the TRC. It has to be noted that none of the 3D_We specimens did exhibit a post-cracking stage, although all 3D_We-t samples did display a proper post-cracking stage during testing. This is explained by the higher position of the reinforcements in the cross-sections, as seen in Figure 3. An apparent deviation of the post-cracking stiffness between the samples of 2D_Wa can also be observed, most certainly due to the accidental casting process in two stages.

Comparisons between the flexural parameters calculated (Table 4) and the experimental curves (Figure 5) can be made. The warp direction exhibits a failure load more than two times the one of the weft and a displacement at failure that is up to three times greater than for the weft direction, independently of the type of textile used (2D or 3D). For 3D_We-t, where the 3D textiles are placed on the very bottom of the cross-section, the reaction force is similar to the one of 3D_Wa specimens. However, the displacement at failure remains significantly lower for the 3D_We-t specimens.

On the other hand, notable improvements are also seen when comparing 2D and 3D reinforcements. In the warp direction, the failure load of 3D_Wa is about 75% of the failure load of 2D_Wa, but the displacement at failure is slightly higher for the 3D textiles than for the 2D ones. Contrarily, in the weft direction, the failure load of the 2D textiles is around 75% of the one of the 3D textiles. Additionally, the displacement at failure of 3D_We-t is almost twice as significant as for 2D_We. 2D reinforcements exhibit a higher post-cracking stiffness than 3D ones, independently of the reinforcing direction.

Figure 6: Comparison between typical curves from each configuration

The pre-cracking stiffness is mostly the same for all the samples except for 3D_We-t. This is unexpected, as all the samples were cast using the same matrix. However, the post-cracking stiffness varies between the compositions, with a minimum value of 30 N/mm for 3D_Wa, and a maximum value of 48 N/mm for 2D_We.

Table 4: Average flexural parameters for each composition (with standard deviation)

	2D Wa	2D We	3D Wa	3D We	3D We-t
Cracking load (kN)	241 ± 26	284 ± 22	237 ± 14	256 ± 18	251 ± 35
Failure load (kN)	661 ± 108	353 ± 15	495 ± 74	/	479 ± 29
Pre-cracking stiffness (N/mm)	822 ± 276	977 ± 20	775 ± 184	811 ± 362	547 ± 52
Post-cracking stiffness (N/mm)	42 ± 10	48 ± 5	30 ± 3	/	42 ± 3

Crack Analysis

Figure 7 shows the horizontal strain analysis (along the length of the samples) as calculated from Vic-3D 9 at a displacement of 5 mm for one typical specimen from each configuration. An analysis of the crack opening was done at a displacement of 3 and 5 mm for all samples and additionally at 10 mm for the samples that achieved such a high deflection.

The different parameters related to the crack openings illustrate the association between the matrix and the textiles. A higher number of cracks in a sample shows that the forces are better redistributed from the matrix to the fibers once the matrix locally fails. A crack with a smaller width shows a better frictional force between the matrix and the fibers and thus, less slippage of the reinforcements and better anchorage. The crack spacing goes in pairs with the number of cracks; if more cracks are present, the spacing between them will be less, and vice versa.

Figure 8 shows the crack development in sample 3D_Wa-4. The vertical jumps depict the crack openings, while the horizontal segments show the spacing between them. An illustration of the crack formation during testing can be seen in Figure 8, where the crack analysis is shown for specimen 3D_Wa-4.

Figure 7: DIC strain and crack analysis

Figure 8: DIC crack opening analysis for sample 3D_Wa-4

The results of the crack analysis done on all specimens can be found in Table 5, where the averages of cracks, crack width, and crack spacing are presented for a displacement of 5 mm. The numbers show that specimens with reinforcements in the warp direction display a larger number of cracks than the weft specimens. The same observation can be done for specimens with 2D reinforcements that present a higher number of cracks than specimens with 3D reinforcements. The crack spacing is inversely related to the number of cracks. Therefore, compositions with a larger number of cracks will have smaller spacing between the cracks. Identical results are shown for crack width, which is in general smaller when reinforcements are in the warp direction and made out of 2D textiles.

Table 5: Average cracks parameters for each composition

	2D Wa	2D We	3D Wa	3D We	3D We-t
Number of cracks (at 5 mm) (-)	10 ± 2	4 ± 1	7 ± 1	2 ± 1	6 ± 0
Crack width (mm)	0,090 ± 0,048	0,301 ± 0,213	0,143 ± 0,061	0,534 ± 0,217	0,152 ± 0,085
Crack spacing (mm)	11,70 ± 6,62	24,77 ± 13,34	17,26 ± 8,57	18,80 ± 22,31	18,83 ± 9,97

DISCUSSION

As seen in the results, the flexural behavior of the TRC in bending is superior (higher reaction force, more significant displacement, and higher post-cracking stiffness) when the reinforcements are in the warp direction instead of the weft and when 2D textiles are used instead of 3D ones. Those results are contradictory to what is currently seen in the literature. Studies showed that 3D textiles perform better than 2D textiles in flexural applications due to the additional anchorage provided by the transversal connections (Amzaleg et al., 2013; El Kadi et al., 2020). Additionally, in cement composites, TRCs with reinforcement in the weft direction are reportedly stronger than those with reinforcement in the warp direction (Dvorkin et al., 2013).

Multiple factors influence the results obtained in this study. First, it must be noted that a volume fraction of 0.48-0.52% of the TRC compositions is relatively low compared to some other studies where reinforcement ratios such as 1.49% are used (El Kadi et al., 2020). Such a small amount of reinforcement can negatively impact the statistical distribution of the results (such as the post-cracking stiffness and the reaction force at failure), making it so that sometimes the samples will fail right after the first crack, such as for 3D_We samples. An increase of 3 mm of the reinforcement spacing from the specimen's bottom side means a change of nearly 20% of the total thickness of the specimens, which led to no post-cracking stage for 3D_We specimens.

The comparison between 2D and 3D reinforcements is also not fully rigorous, as the spacing between the lower layer of textiles and the bottom side of the specimen is not always exactly 2 mm. 3D_Wa, 3D_We, and 3D_We-t had a spacing of 2.6 mm, 5.1 mm, and 1 mm, respectively. Also, due to the casting process, the 2D reinforcements are slightly tensioned during the clamping, which could positively influence the mechanical behavior. Lastly, the anchorage of the 3D textiles, which is beneficial when the textiles are coated, reinforces the clamping of the outside fibers of yarns bundles but might damage the fibers instead.

Finally, the improvement of the textiles' warp directions from the weft directions can be due to the extra yarn of polyester present in the warp direction. The addition of the yarn fibers not being straight from the start explains the more significant displacement achieved in the 2D_Wa and 3D_Wa samples.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the flexural behavior of TRC samples reinforced by woven textiles of different geometry and orientation. The geometry and orientation of textile reinforcement also play an important role in flexural behavior. Using reinforcements in the warp direction leads to greater displacement before failure, and using 2D textiles leads to increased strength.

It can be concluded that the reinforcement ratio greatly influences the flexural behavior of TRC samples. Indeed, for a small ratio, the positioning of the reinforcements becomes critical, and an incorrect location can detriment the use of the reinforcements.

FUTURE WORK

Multiple paths open according to those results. It would be interesting to explore the effect of coating on the textiles to measure the improvement compared to the uncoated textiles. It is expected that coated textiles will have an enhanced behavior as the fiber bundles would be able to transfer the loads more uniformly and have a better anchorage in the matrix. The impact of a higher reinforcement ratio could also be analyzed by using additional layers of 2D textiles or by stitching 2D textiles to 3D textiles. A more focused way would be to concentrate the textiles reinforcements only in the tensile zone of the section.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research is funded by the Fonds Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek (FWO) as part of an SBO project, "A new generation of high-performance buildings integrating aerogels and textiles reinforced composite" (S008023N)

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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